

Release of nitrous oxide from the global coastal ocean: interactions with ecosystems and humans (*Nitractions*)

1 Excellence

1.1 State of the art, knowledge needs and project objectives

Nitrous oxide (N_2O)—a strong greenhouse gas and a cause of ozone layer depletion—is released from land, seawater and its sediment into the atmosphere [26, 37, 41]. This release is aggravated by the production and use of nitrogen fertilisers worldwide [13, 26]. About one third of N_2O emissions comes from the ocean [36], most of which is formed in the coastal ocean¹ because of the fast turn-over and the interaction with the land. The quantification of the N_2O flux from the ocean is uncertain [46]. We want to know these fluxes, because after carbon dioxide (CO_2) and methane (CH_4) [3, 39, 40], N_2O is the third most important long-lived greenhouse gas [36]. The basic mechanisms of biochemical reactions of nitrogen compounds (also called *reactive nitrogen*, Nr) are largely known, but there are issues making it difficult to make quantitative predictions [24, 35]. Firstly, it has not been well quantified how much the different reactions contribute; this depends on a lot of circumstances, environmental (e.g. temperature) [20, 34] and biochemical (e.g. presence of N_2O reductase inhibitors) [18, 9, 27, pp. 767–9] alike. Secondly, the integration of the different processes and their parameterisations—needed for any large-scale modelling—are introducing errors and uncertainties [e.g. 19, pp. 4–5]. To quantify the N_2O fluxes these issues must be addressed.

The surplus creation of N_2O is but one aspect of the disturbance of the nitrogen cycle by humans [1, 11, 17, 29, 42]. Processes in the coastal ocean—where there is interaction with land and the turn-overs of nitrogen and carbon are fast—are uncertain and may have large effects on the environment and climate. Changes in the nitrogen cycle, amongst other environmental changes, bring with them hazards like eutrophication and oxygen (O_2) depletion in marginal seas. Some but not all of the N_2O is converted by the enzyme nitrous oxide reductase in bacteria into dinitrogen (N_2). The release of surplus N_2O into the atmosphere causes global warming, also heating the oceans and tending to decrease O_2 concentrations [e.g. 4], which in turn may cause more formation of N_2O and CH_4 [22, 47]. All these aspects bring us back to the necessity of realistic parameterisation and simulation of the nitrogen cycle.

Others have been modelling the nitrogen cycle within larger biogeochemical ocean (and coupled) models [25, 45], including N_2O [16, 17, 33]. However, as of yet there are both fundamental and integrational issues [24]. We may address those by the use of the state-of-the-art biogeochemical ocean general circulation model BLOM/iHAMOCC² (also a component in the Norwegian Earth System Model, NorESM) [38]. By focusing on the formation of N_2O , we may reduce the complexity of the plethora of processes in the nitrogen cycle.

Primary objective. We will quantify the N_2O released from the ocean into the atmosphere, based on the physical and chemical pathways of nitrogen in the coastal ocean.

Secondary objectives.

1. We will model the N_2O sources and sinks in the seawater and sediments (in the ocean model BLOM/iHAMOCC) (realised in WP1 and WP2).
2. We will create a dataset of time-dependent maps of the amount of N_2O released from the sediment and seawater into the atmosphere, derived from the model simulations (realised in WP3).
3. We will quantify the influence of the inflow of anthropogenic nitrogen compounds into the sea on N_2O fluxes from the sea (realised in WP3).

¹The *coastal ocean* is the region between the continent and the open ocean, including the continental shelf and slope, and most attached waters like estuaries. This definition mostly coincides with that of the *continental margin* [19].

²Bergen Layered Ocean Model/isopycnic HAMburg Ocean Carbon Cycle.

1.2 Research questions and hypotheses, theoretical approach and methodology

In this project we aim to answer two main questions:

- How much N_2O is released from the coastal ocean to the atmosphere?
- How much of this is attributable to Nr inputs from coastal processes?

Release of N_2O . Nitrous oxide is released from land, the coastal ocean and the open ocean. After determining the contribution of the oceans and the coastal ocean, we can compare that with other studies of N_2 , N_2O and ammonia (NH_3) released globally and from the different Earth system components. Our estimate aims to constrain the absolute flux of N_2O (as well as NH_3 and N_2) on a national to global scale, as well as to determine the relative contribution of coastal, sedimental and open ocean fluxes compared to land.

Attribution to Nr inputs. Natural ecosystems produce different nitrogen compounds through nitrification and incomplete denitrification [10, 18, 43]. Nitrification changes one form of Nr (NH_3) to another (nitrite, NO_2^- , and nitrate, NO_3^-). Denitrification is a sink for Nr (since the N_2 that it produces is only bioavailable to nitrogen fixing bacteria), and not a source; incomplete denitrification may convert one form of Nr (NO_3^-) to others (NO_2^- , NO , N_2O) [e.g. 13]. Agriculture and aquaculture are strongly perturbing the supply of Nr to the surrounding ecosystems, including the coastal ocean, mainly because of fertilisation practices [12, 29, 41]. In addition, atmospheric deposition of anthropogenic Nr is caused by the combustion of fossil fuels as well as the production and use of fertilisers [8]. This creates a chain of processes leading to, among other things, increased concentrations of nitrogen compounds and a different mixture thereof as part of the altered nitrogen cycle. The nitrogen cycle is being perturbed strongly [32],³ and it may cause significant changes in the release of N_2O but estimates of the anthropogenic contribution through Nr input differ [8, 17].

Methodology. Through modelling, we will determine the nitrogen pathways that are most relevant to quantify N_2O fluxes and budgets on a national to global scale. It will be especially important to include ammonium oxidation, anammox⁴ and nitrate reduction. These biogeochemical pathways are not yet properly captured by global models [2, 35]. There are especially large uncertainties in the net N_2O produced by nitrification in the surface of the ocean [47, 48]. Ongoing development on the isopycnic ocean GCM (BLOM) is intended to improve the treatment of the upper part of the ocean, which should help with this issue. The biogeochemistry module (iHAMOCC) already includes a number of nitrogen compounds and pathways, and is a good basis for testing and extending the nitrogen cycle description on global and regional scales.

In BLOM/iHAMOCC in the euphotic layer photosynthesis takes place, where organic matter is created. For this light, CO_2 , water and nutrients are needed. The nutrients, nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), silicon (Si) and iron (Fe), enter the ocean through atmospheric deposition and riverine inflow. Carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus are incorporated a stoichiometric ratio of $\text{P}:\text{N}:\text{C} = 1:16:122$. Plankton excrete and die and the resulting particles sink down (with a velocity increasing with depth, and the model has the option to enable particle aggregation. Throughout the model ocean remineralisation takes place and the nutrients are available again for primary production whenever they are in the euphotic zone. Where, when and how fast they are used for primary production depends on the light intensity, temperature, the limiting nutrient and grazing. See Tjiputra et al. [38] for further details about iHAMOCC, including a discussion of the reproduction of the NO_3^- and O_2 distributions. The model does not yet include ammonium (NH_4^+) as a separate tracer.

Particulate organic matter that does not remineralise ultimately reaches the seafloor. BLOM/iHAMOCC includes an early diagenesis module that allows to quantify interactions between the sediment (bioturbated zone) and the free water column [14]. The sediment module will be upgraded

³These issues depend on the planetary boundaries for the nitrogen cycle [28, 31], which may have been set lower than necessary [42].

⁴Anaerobic ammonium oxidation. Anammox does not produce N_2O like incomplete denitrification does, but it is an alternative pathway to N_2 , shortcutting—and thus influencing— N_2O production [5, 6].

to also allow predictive simulations of N_2O from sedimentary processes (such as nitrification and denitrification). These tasks will be part of work package 1 (see the flowchart).

When N_2O , NH_3 and N_2 are produced and transported through the sea, they will inevitably make contact with and largely flux into the atmosphere [e.g. 30]. The interaction between the ocean and the atmosphere is part of work package 2.

In work package 3, the relationship between Nr inputs and N_2O outflux will be quantified. The Nr inputs to be modelled include the dissolved species NO_3^- , NO_2^- and NH_4^+ . In addition, the marine Nr sinks are N_2O , NO and NH_3 (flux out of the sea). The N_2O fluxes are provided in work package 2. The Nr fluxes will come from existing data products and collaboration partners. Then an analysis will be done to correlate N_2O with Nr fluxes, and see to what extent N_2O outfluxes can be attributed to Nr .

Risk assessment. The spatial resolution in the model is, at the moment, low for the coastal ocean (however, the implementation of the new processes is essential for emerging higher resolution versions of ESMs, such as NorESM2-HR). Shortcomings in both resolution and process detail may result in an unreliable model and thus, potentially, unrealistic results. Other, already funded projects have a stronger focus on the resolution issue. Therefore it is *likely* that a model configuration will be available with a sufficiently high resolution. In the case we will not such a configuration available in time, this will be *harmful* for Deliverables 2 and 3 (the papers and the summary for policy makers). We estimate the risk of those potential shortcomings to be *moderate*. In any case, it will be beneficial to have coastal ocean relevant processes already included in a coarser resolution biogeochemical ocean model in order to provide and test the processes that become relevant at higher resolutions.

Side effects. Travels are included in the budget of the proposal (up to seven trips, one trip per person per year). Low-fossil-fuel travels will be preferred. If aviation is needed, emissions will be offset.

Application of knowledge. The N_2O fluxes are to be used by the climate research community to make better projections of climate change. In the light of the Paris Agreement [23], planetary boundaries [31] and the UN’s sustainable development goals, our quantification of the increased fluxes will also be of direct use to policy makers. This project will also result in improved insight in the effect of Nr on ecosystems. With our quantitative model we might find a strong connection between Nr and eutrophication, hypoxia and fish stocks. This can inform the fish industry, the government and other potential stakeholders on what may happen and how the situation can be improved.

1.3 Novelty and ambition

We plan to realise an improved representation of the nitrogen cycle with better flux estimates of N_2O in the ocean module of the Norwegian Earth System Model (NorESM), which is a leading-edge advanced climate model. At the moment there is a strong focus on CO_2 in climate projections. With our development, a more realistic radiative forcing including N_2O can—and must—be used in CMIP7 simulations.

Methodology. The nitrogen cycles in state-of-the-art Earth system models are incomplete or not sufficiently tested for determining N_2O fluxes. Through the state-of-the-art ocean model BLOM/

iHAMOCC—as part of the Norwegian Earth system model (NorESM)—we will examine our research questions.

The biogeochemical tracers are simulated by iHAMOCC—both for the sediment and the water column—and advected and mixed by the general circulation model BLOM. This model is being actively developed in Oslo and Bergen. Many improvements concerning tracer inputs and isotopes, among other things, have been performed [38], and other efforts for more efficient model simulations, code refactoring and clean-up are underway, partly by the applicant as part of the EU project *CRESCENDO* (finishing in 2020), and partly as part of the ongoing NFR project *INES* led by NORCE with UiB as one of the host institutes. The goal of the latter project is to develop NorESM and, among other things, contribute to preparing it for the CMIP7 simulations. As the development of NorESM is important for us and the inclusion of relevant greenhouse gasses is important for them, it is essential that we work together.

Reactive nitrogen enters the coastal ocean by river and groundwater inflow, as well as atmospheric deposition. The former source is an existing option in NorESM based on NEWS 2 from Mayorga et al. [21]. Atmospheric deposition input data is available from CMIP6.

The water column and sediment porewaters of iHAMOCC already includes N_2 and NO_3^- . The water column also contains N_2O . However, since the latest developments of the nitrogen tracers in the model, there have been new insights in the nitrogen cycle, including the role of anammox, dissimilatory nitrate reduction and other pathways of denitrification [9, 24, 35, 41]. Also, the sediment does not contain N_2O as of yet. Hence it is clear that we have to revisit the nitrogen tracers, its equations (parameterisations) and parameters and verify them against available observations. The observations can be found in the online database MEMENTO of *Marine Methane and Nitrous Oxide*. For the verification of the model we will visually compare with ComPlot and use established statistical methods with Julia and any other relevant tools.

Specifically, task 1.1 will entail the inclusion of N_2O in the sediment, and to make the parameterisations involving N_2O in particular, and any N tracer in general, in the water column and the sediment porewaters as universal as possible in a modelling context. We plan to add ammonium (NH_4^+) and ammonia (NH_3) to the model, as well as nitrate and nitrite, as separate tracers. The first results should make clear if further refinement is needed for a reliable model and realistic N_2O emissions.⁵ Quantifying NH_3 emissions is a pertinent desideratum, and therefore NH_3 and NH_4^+ should be included in any case (also because the ion NH_4^+ acts as a central N redox state in the biogeochemical N cycle).

The combination of a state-of-the-art ocean biogeochemical model as part of an ESM framework, namely NorESM, and the fact that it includes an actively participating sediment component, and the need for constraining N_2O emissions in climate projections, makes this project novel and ambitious.

2 Impact

2.1 Potential for academic impact of the research project

The **coastal ocean modelling community** will benefit from our improved representation of the nitrogen cycle, especially because of our global process-based approach to the determination of N_2O fluxes in the coastal ocean. In contrast to regional models, our global model has the advantage to not have open boundaries in the ocean domain and is thus free from unreliable boundary conditions and drift that occur in regional biogeochemical ocean models. The improved model should lead to a more realistic description of plankton blooms and O_2 concentrations throughout the water column. This increases confidence in simulated concentrations of the tracers in the sea, including N_2O . Since N_2O will contribute to the radiative forcing, the **climate research community** will benefit from our N_2O flux estimates.

⁵*Reliable* means not only having a good similitude with observations but also being good in a more process-based sense.[e.g. 15, p. 52]. Of course, in numerical modelling a good balance must be found between that type of reliability and the extent of underdetermination.

Target audience	Expected output	Engagement	Impact
Ocean modelling community	Improved representation of the nitrogen cycle especially N ₂ O and NH ₃	Publications, e.g. in <i>Biogeosciences</i> ; topical conference	More accurate and capable model of the N and C cycles
Climate research community	Data product of N ₂ O flux maps out of the ocean	A publication on the estimation of N ₂ O fluxes	Improved accuracy of climate change projections
Society – people interested in science and climate change	Improved nitrogen cycle including estimates of N ₂ O fluxes	Popular article; news release via BCCR PR office	Increased awareness of non-CO ₂ greenhouse gasses and food production
Society – policy makers	Recommendations for nutrient management in agriculture	Report to be shared with relevant organisations	Stabilisation of biodiversity in the coastal ocean, and sustainable fishing and aquafarming

Table 1: Relevant outputs and impacts for different stake holders.

2.2 Potential for societal impact of the research project

In Section 1.2 we refer to the Paris agreement and the SDGs, as well as aquaculture. Concretely, this project has the following societal impacts:

- With realistic fluxes of N₂O included in Earth system models, climate projections may become more accurate, which is important for meeting the targets set by the Paris Agreement (SDG 13).
- Based on our analysis, we may provide guidelines for sustainable nutrient management in agri- and aquaculture. Sustainable nutrient management could keep coastal ocean and climate changes within safe bounds (SDGs 13 and 14). Policy recommendations will be communicated to the Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment and the Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries.
- Changes in concentrations of nitrogen compounds will impact biogeochemical cycles and can cause eutrophication and impact the whole ecosystem, including fisheries [e.g. 27, pp. 637–9]. The above-mentioned policies should limit cases of eutrophication and improve fish ecosystems, including biodiversity as stipulated by the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (SDG 14).
- Unconstrained use of fertilisers can lead to marginally increased harvest yields in agriculture but brings along the risk of large changes in ecosystems; this is a *tragedy of the commons*. In other words, sustainable nutrient management is necessary for food security (SDG 2).

2.3 Measures for communication and exploitation

Target audiences (first column in Table 1) include the ocean modelling community and the climate research community. We will also engage with people interested in climate change, and with policy makers to communicate sustainable aqua- and agricultural nutrient management. One conference we will certainly participate in is the 52nd Liège Colloquium on Ocean Dynamics, which is about human impacts on coastal marine environments. As this conference already takes place in the second quarter of the project, the aim will be to learn and make acquaintances in the different communities instead of disseminating any significant results.

Dissemination will happen in several ways, firstly through peer-reviewed publications. At least one of these papers will be on scientific understanding of the nitrogen cycle (in the coastal ocean), to be published in EGU’s *Biogeosciences* or another open access journal. A second paper, and associated

report for policy makers, will be on Nr inputs and N₂O fluxes, to be published as open access in a journal suited for the climate research community. Secondly, we plan to actively participate in one or more conferences (in addition to the one in Liège). Which ones are to be decided. Finally, we plan to publish a popular article, disseminated through different channels including the PR office of the Bjerknes Center for Climate Research (BCCR), and on forskning.no and/or the associated ScienceNordic to reach a wide audience. The final row in Table 1 is for policy makers; at least the aforementioned ministries will receive a report on the findings that could guide their decision-making process.

3 Implementation

3.1 Project manager and project group

The principle investigator (PI) of the leading organisation, **UiB**, is Marco van Hulten. He has a biogeochemical ocean modelling background (see his CV). As a result of his recent involvement in the development of BLOM/iHAMOCC and NorESM, he is aware of strengths and weaknesses of the ocean model and model framework. The human perturbation of the nitrogen cycle comes mostly from agricultural practises and are therefore studied by those outside the field of oceanography. Nonetheless the ocean—especially the coastal ocean, or so we would further investigate—is a main component in this perturbation and a significant emitter of N₂O. An oceanographic point of view in combination with an integrated modelling approach is therefore needed.

NORCE–Climate will be our main partner with Augustin Kessler as the PI. The roles for UiB and NORCE will be further described in the next section. We will also work with Caitlin Frame from the **New York State Department of Environmental Conservation**. She has many years of scientific experience in the field of N₂O, and the nitrogen and other biogeochemical cycles. Her knowledge on the subject will provide a very useful basis for our modelling work.

3.2 Project organisation and management

On the last page, a Gantt chart is presented with the different work packages and their subdivision into tasks. The two researchers on the project are henceforth designated as *researcher 1* (UiB) for the whole four-year project term and *researcher 2* (NORCE) for three years. The project will be coordinated by the researcher 1, with help from the administrative support team at UiB.

	UiB	NORCE
Task 1.1	✓	
Task 1.2		✓
Deliverable 1	✓	
Task 2.1	✓	
Task 2.2		✓
Task 3.1		✓
Deliverable 2		✓
Task 3.2	✓	
Deliverable 3	✓	
Deliverable 4	✓	

Table 2: Division of tasks: for each task, the responsible organisations is marked.

Work package 1 starts with the task (1.1) of improving the nitrogen cycle in the ocean model, which will be executed by researcher 1. Within a year, the first results from simulations are expected and should be analysed; this coincides with the start of researcher 2. Table 2 shows the complete division of tasks for the two institutes. The modelling and analysis will be reported on in a peer-reviewed publication in the third year.

Work package 2 starts near the end of the second year, and overlaps with work package 1. Task 2.1 is a continuation of Task 1.1, but WP 2 focusses on the interaction of N₂, N₂O and NH₃ between the ocean and the atmosphere [44]. BLOM/iHAMOCC is then run within NorESM but uncoupled from the other components (forced).

The main goal of **work package 3** is to arrive at a time-dependent flux of N₂O (and maybe NH₃) from the ocean to the atmosphere (2+1 dimensional dataset). This dataset will be useful for several purposes, namely in itself to inform on the distribution and variability, and it may be a usable forcing climatology for chemical atmospheric General Circulation Models (GCMs) [7] and as part of—or constraint on—ESMs including the next version of NorESM. As such, in addition to a dataset (Deliverable 2), there will be a paper and executive summary on the impact—especially the N₂O outflux—for the ministries mentioned in Section 2.2.

Work package 4 overarches all tasks related to data management and dissemination of results. UiB/researcher 1 is responsible for this. Since the first year is used for model development, the use of work package 4 becomes relevant only in the second year of the project. Deliverable 4 has a more overarching nature than the other deliverables and is therefore put under work package 4.

The Bjerknes Climate Data Centre at the University of Bergen will ensure professional stewardship of all observational and model output data generated. A data management plan will provide information on what data will be generated, it will ensure curation, preservation, and ensure open access to all results generated. The data management plan will follow the requirements as outlined by the Research Council of Norway and by the Open Research Data Pilot as required within H2020 and ensure that data is made available following the FAIR data management principles. Works derived from this project will be made available under a free licence through an approved national or international data repository by the end of the project.

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